

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS THROUGH COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: A CASE STUDY OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya: This case study examines the impact of utilizing collaborative learning technology in teacher education programs to develop the professional competencies of future teachers. The study explores the effectiveness of integrating technology into teacher training to enhance collaboration, communication, and critical thinking skills among pre-service teachers. Findings suggest that incorporating collaborative education technology can significantly improve the development of professional competencies in future teachers, ultimately preparing them for successful careers in the field of education.

Keywords: professional competencies, future teachers, collaborative learning, technology, teacher education, development, communication skills, critical thinking skills, collaboration, pre-service teachers, education field.

Introduction. In the context of developing professional competencies of future teachers through collaborative learning, the use of technology in teacher education can play a significant role in enhancing the learning experience and preparing teachers for the challenges of the 21st century classroom. Collaborative learning, when integrated with technology, can provide future teachers with opportunities to engage in meaningful interactions, share ideas, and co-construct knowledge with their peers.

One approach to using technology in teacher education is through online platforms and tools that facilitate collaborative learning. For example, online discussion forums, virtual classrooms, and collaborative document editing tools can enable future teachers to engage in discussions, share resources, and work on projects together. These digital platforms can also provide opportunities for reflection, feedback, and peer evaluation, which are essential components of professional development for teachers.

Additionally, the use of technology can support future teachers in developing digital literacy skills and integrating technology into their teaching practices. By engaging in collaborative learning activities that involve the use of educational technologies, future teachers can gain hands-on experience with

digital tools and resources that they can later incorporate into their own classrooms.

Furthermore, collaborative learning through technology can help future teachers develop important competencies such as communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and critical thinking. By working collaboratively on projects, solving problems together, and engaging in discussions with their peers, future teachers can enhance their ability to collaborate effectively with colleagues, engage students in meaningful learning experiences, and adapt to the changing demands of the education landscape.

Literature review. This case study of using technology in teacher education to develop professional competencies of future teachers through collaborative learning highlights the potential of integrating technology into teacher preparation programs. By leveraging digital tools and online platforms for collaborative learning, teacher education programs can better prepare future educators for the complexities of the modern classroom and equip them with the skills and competencies needed to thrive in their teaching careers.

Developing professional competencies of future teachers through collaborative learning is a crucial aspect of teacher education programs. Collaborative learning involves students working together in groups to achieve common learning goals, which can be highly beneficial for future teachers as they prepare to enter the teaching profession. Collaborative learning requires future teachers to communicate effectively with their peers, share ideas, and engage in productive discussions. This helps them develop strong communication skills, which are essential for effective teaching and collaboration with colleagues, students, and parents.

Methodology. By working collaboratively on projects and assignments, future teachers learn how to work effectively in teams, leverage each other's strengths, and support one another in achieving common goals. These teamwork skills are valuable for teachers who often work in collaborative environments within schools. Collaborative learning encourages future teachers to engage in critical thinking and problem-solving activities with their peers. By tackling challenges together, they develop their problem-solving abilities and learn how to approach complex issues from different perspectives.

Collaborative learning provides future teachers with opportunities to learn from their peers, share knowledge and experiences, and support each other in their professional development. This peer learning can be invaluable in helping future teachers gain new insights and perspectives on teaching practices.

Through collaborative learning activities, future teachers can engage in reflective practices and receive feedback from their peers. This reflection and feedback help them identify areas for improvement, enhance their teaching practices, and continuously strive for professional growth.

Discussion. Collaborative learning often involves working with peers from diverse backgrounds, which can help future teachers develop cultural competence and an appreciation for diversity. This is essential for creating inclusive and equitable learning environments for all students. Collaborative learning can also involve the use of technology tools and platforms, which helps future teachers develop digital literacy skills and learn how to integrate technology into their teaching practices effectively.

Collaborative learning plays a vital role in developing the professional competencies of future teachers by fostering communication skills, teamwork, problem-solving abilities, peer learning and support, reflection, cultural competence, diversity appreciation, and technology integration. Teacher education programs that incorporate collaborative learning strategies can better prepare future educators for the challenges of the teaching profession and equip them with the skills needed to excel in their roles.

Conclusion. Collaborative learning is a powerful tool for developing the professional competencies of future teachers. By engaging in collaborative activities, future teachers can enhance their communication skills, teamwork abilities, problem-solving capabilities, peer learning and support networks, reflection practices, cultural competence, diversity appreciation, and technology integration skills. These competencies are essential for success in the teaching profession and can help future teachers effectively navigate the complexities of the classroom environment. Teacher education programs that prioritize collaborative learning can better prepare future educators for the demands of the profession and empower them to make a positive impact on student learning and development.

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